

A Journal of the Faculty of Arts
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

THE
INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL

**OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH
IN HUMANITIES (INJOCORH)**

ISSN 3026-9067

Volume 2 Number 1 2024

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. Anjola ROBBIN

Consulting Editor

Dr. Michael Olayinka GBADEGESIN

Managing Editors

Dr. Emmanuel UZOJI

Dr. Rachel Oluwafisayo ALUKO

Dr. Peter Ayoola ODERINDE

Dr. Jimmy AKOH

Corresponding Editor

Dr. Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI

Phonological Analysis of Consonant Clusters in Tiv Language

Msuega AHAR

Department of Languages and Linguistics, Benue State University, Makurdi
msuegahar@gmail.com, +2348064835183

Jighjigh Leo Justus ISHIMA

Department of Languages and Linguistics, Benue State University, Makurdi

Abstract

The paper investigates the role of consonant clusters in the phonological structure of Tiv language focusing on their identification, contribution to the language and influence on syllable patterns. The study identifies and categorises consonant clusters present in Tiv language, explores the contribution of these consonant clusters to the phonological system of Tiv to examine their distribution and categorises how these consonant clusters influence syllables structures in the language. The descriptive design is used as the method of research analysis while qualitative approach is used for the interpretation of data. Data is collected using observation as the primary source and journals and textbooks serve as secondary sources. The researcher uses the Structuralist Theory of linguistics proposed by Ferdinand de Saussure in 1916 as basis for analysis. The study establishes that, the language allows consonant clusters of two to four across Tiv phonological structures. Their distributional is however gradient in nature, and they contribute to giving unique phonological structure and also create complex onset, complex coda and ambisyllabic syllables in the Tiv language.

Keywords: Consonant, Clusters, Phonology, Sound, Tiv Language

Introduction

Consonant cluster as a linguistic feature in Tiv plays a vital role in phonological and morphological structures in the Tiv language, predominantly spoken in Benue State, Middle Belt of Nigeria. Consonant clusters are a constituent of two and more consonants without the inclusion of vowels in between them. They constitute one of the phonological structural complexities of the Tiv language.

The Tiv phonological system allows the varying shapes of consonants clusters, which contribute to the distinct sound patterns of the Tiv language. These clusters can occur at the beginning, middle, and final positions of syllables or words. However, their distribution in and across the language is governed by specific phonotactic rules of the language (Aboh, 2004). For example, combinations such as: “ng”, “gb”, “mb” are common in Tiv, revealing the language’s phonetic richness and aiding in lexical differentiation (Ikoro, 1996).

Additionally, consonant clusters provide a basis for various kinds of syllables in Tiv, allowing the formation of rhythm and flow of speech. The allowable, possible clusters and their present in Tiv shapes how words are constructed and articulated, adding to the language’s distinct prosodic features (Aboh, 2004). Phonologically, various words reveal varying kinds of consonant structures, including affixation. Prefixes and infixes in the Tiv language which result in contributing sound structures which are crucial for indicating grammatical aspects such as tense, aspect and plurality (Gerhardf, 1983). This presence and use of clusters account for the systematic versatility of the language.

In both language acquisition and second language learning (L2), the mastery of consonant clusters is a necessary knowledge for native speakers and learners. Clusters generally pose challenge because of their complexities and then accounting for their importance in the linguistic knowledge of the speakers.

Statement of Problem

Generally, phonological structure is language specific, in like manner Tiv phonology is peculiar, housing many consonant clusters. These consonant clusters pose challenges in speaking, reading, learning and understanding the Tiv language. This introduces irregular or inconsistent pronunciations by various speakers of the language, and affects effective communication which is the core purpose of language. The

study aims at examining such clusters to enhance understanding as to aid the communication process in the language.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This paper aims at investigating and analysing the role of consonant clusters in the phonological structure of the Tiv language and to reveal their influence on lexical differentiation and syllable structure of the language. And the research has the following objectives:

1. to identify the consonant clusters in the Tiv language;
2. to explore how consonant clusters contribute to distinguishing between different words in Tiv; and
3. to analyse the influence of the consonant cluster on the syllable structure of Tiv.

Research Methodology

The research design adopted in this paper is purposive or non-probability sampling (Patton, 2002). The instrument used in the collection of data was observational method and oral interview was carried out by the researchers. The researchers interacted with native speakers of the Tiv language to assess the speech pattern expressed through oral interaction. The researchers picked sound structure that contained consonant clusters in Tiv phonological inventory. The sample of 19 consonant clusters constituted primary sources for the needed analysis. The researchers jotted down those consonant clusters that captured the subject matter. The presentation was made with the aid of tables to enhance meaningful and easy interpretation of the data obtained through observation. The qualitative analysis of the data was carried out concerning each of the study objectives.

Literature Review

Few concepts within this subject matter were explained to ensure good understanding and comprehension of the linguistic situation captured under this study. Some of these concepts include consonants, clusters, Tiv and Language. According to Roach (2010), "The words vowel and consonant are very familiar ones but, when we study the sounds of speech scientifically, we find that it is not easy to define exactly what they mean". This means that sounds contain so much and studies on them can reveal many aspects depending on what the study focus to achieve.

Consonants: Hamann and Schmitz (2005) submit that, "consonants are often classified by being given a so-called voicing place and manner of articulation-label. Voicing means that the vocal folds vibrate or not: if they do not, the sound is voiceless (note that vowels always imply the use of vocal folds). the place of articulation is the place where the airflow will be more or less obstructed. Manner is concerned with the nature of the obstruction".

The above scholars have expressed their view of what consonant embrace. From their opinion consonant contain three major characteristics. These characteristics are the basic and obvious features which determine their classifications. Similarly, consonants are so integral in every human language; this is because they play a major role in the phonological system of languages. They are important to the intelligibility and clarity of speech, creating distinction between words and words' meanings. Language building its sound system which houses more complex forms of communication (O'Grady, Chibald, Aronoff & Rees-Millar, 2010).

Consonant clusters are a linguistic situation where more than one consonant form sound combinations in words of a given language. Crystal (2011:103) argues that, "From a phonological point of view, consonants are those units which function at the margins of syllables, either singly or in clusters. This means that consonant also form clusters". Consonant cluster refers to co-occurrence of two or more consonant without an intervening vowel. Consonant clusters constitute unit of language which has it unique contribution in the phonology of languages in addition to single consonants. And they must be understood as separate units of linguistic structure. This calls for the study and analysis of consonant clusters in Tiv language.

Consonant clusters are in the domain of phonology in language study which deals with how sounds structure of consonants sounds is arranged and patterned into acceptable and permissible structures. It is guided by certain phonotactic rules: for instance, in English, consonant clusters that are allowed at the onset cannot be more than three and not more than four at the coda. This is represented with this notation. Danham and Lobeck (2013) maintain that, “In English, an onset can consist of one to three cluster of consonants. Certain group of two phonemes can occur next to each other at the beginning of a syllable: /fl/, /sp/ and /tr/, among others. Consider which three sounds can occur as the onset of a syllable in English /spl/, /spr/, /skr/, /str/ and the rare /sw/, as in Selevosis”. This expression by the above authors have considered number of consonant clusters in a word generally and their likely position of occurrence or distribution. These however reveal that consonant clusters do not occur arbitrary. They occur according to the acceptable patterning system in particular language. This account for why the authors is specific about what happen in English language. It again reveals that the consonant clusters are acceptable and applicable in a given language may not automatically be acceptable in another language.

In light of the above, consonant clusters are sounds structure made by more than one consonant in given position of words in languages. Consonant cluster operates differently from mere consonants. While, consonants follow specific phonological rules for their articulation and successful distribution in language consonant clusters are subject to more phonotactic constraints which determine allowable or possible combinations of consonants in a particular language. For instance, in English, the cluster /spl/ can occur at the initial of a syllable “as splash” but not at the final position. In Tiv, the cluster /mt/ can be allow at the intial word position in Tiv language but not at the end of a word or syllable (as in Mtem) but not at the end.

Tiv: The term Tiv means different things depending on the context applied. It embraces or could mean ethnic group, language or name of a person. As an ethnic group, Tiv are primarily located in Nigeria, especially in Benue, Nasarawa and Taraba State among others. They are among the Nigeria’s largest monolingual groups (Bohaman, 1953).

As a language, Tiv is spoken by the people also called Tiv. By classification they constitute the membership of the southern Bantoid languages, which is part of the larger Niger Congo language family (Abiodun, 2014). The language is a very crucial unit of the cultural identity of the Tiv people. It houses a unique and rich phonological system that embraces vowel harmony and tonal distinction. It is classified among the languages spoken predominantly in West Africa (Blench, 2019). Historically, the term Tiv refers to the name of the ancestor who is considered as father of the people. According to this philosophy and premise, the name “Tiv” is derived from an ancestor names Tiv, who is considered the progenitor of the people. According to the Tiv oral traditions, all Tiv people trace their link or lineage back to this ancestor, symbolising a common heritage and unity among the group (Bohannan and Bohannan, 1969).

Although the term Tiv is used to mean different things; in this research work, the term is used to mean language, but wherever it refers to the people as an ethnic group indication is made to distinguished it from the former. The Tiv phonological system includes a variety of consonants and vowels alongside the use of tones. According to Orjime (2015), Tiv has nasals (/m/, /n/), stops (/p/, /t/, /b/, /d/) fricatives (/f/, /v/, /s/, /z/) and approximants (/w/, /j/). One of the common features of the Tiv phonological pattern is the presence of prenasalised consonants like /mb/, /nd/ which are not present in English. Prenasalised consonants appear in words when nasals sounds are followed by oral stops or fricatives. They play a role in distinguishing meaning. Tiv also has a rich vowel system with seven oral vowels that can be contrasted with their nasalised counterparts. This system allows varying aspects of phonemic distinctions which are not present in English where nasalisation is not phonemic. The tonal system in Tiv, as marked by Armstrong (1989), embrace high, mid and low tones that are essential for different meaning interpretations.

In contrast, English has more extensive features as consonants, including voiceless and voiced stops (/p/, /k/, /b/, /d/, /g/) fricatives (/t/, /v/, /θ/, /s/, /z/ and affricates (/tʃ/, /dʒ/). English accepts complex consonant clusters, in sequences like /str/ or /spl/. These are not commonly found in most African

languages including Tiv (McWhorter’s 2008). English on the other hand does not have prenasalised consonants, and do not accept nasalisation of vowels in the manner Tiv does.

Language: Language can simply mean the human tool for interaction. In general, language is a complex phenomenon because it is a multifaceted concept which houses many key aspects. O’Grady, Archibald and Katamba (2011) stress that “language is at the heart of all things human we use it when we’re talking, thinking, reading, writing and listening. It’s part of our communities, it forgoes the emotional bond between parent and child, it’s the vehicle for literature and poetry”. This means language engage or deflect in all human activities including the aspect of thinking. It is very productive in human interaction because language enhances human relationship through communication. It is a structured system of communication used by humans consisting of sounds, symbols, and gestures. It allows for the expression of thoughts emotions and ideas (Crystal, 2003). Language as a larger structure contains subunits such as: phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, among others. While the study of language includes all the above various subunits, each of this units may be studied separately to gain understanding of the individual subunits which may give birth to the better understanding of this complex phenomenon called Language. In this study focus is given to the phonology of the Tiv language.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts the Structural Theory of linguistics, which is mostly referred to as structuralism as a framework for analysing language. It emphasises understanding the underlying structures that govern the linguistic systems. Its foundation was laid by Ferdinand de Saussure, a Swiss linguist in 1916. The structuralists generally believe that larger structures can better be understood by understanding the smaller units which make up the larger structure. Language in this case is a bigger structure that can be better understood by its subunits which is the focus of this study.

The key tenets of this theory include language as a system of signs is composed of signs where meaning arises from difference between signs. It also deals with synchronic and diachronic analysis so language is studied as a system at a specific point in time rather than only through historical development. It includes the tenet of phonology and phonemes: here language can be broken down into sound units and their value is determined by their function and contrast within the system. Again, syntagmatic and pragmatic relations. Language elements are structured in a linear sequence and also has associative relations where units are grouped based on function.

Structural theory provides a framework for understanding how consonant clusters interact within the language’s system. Phonemes in consonant clusters are analysed based on their relationships to other phonemes and how they contrast with one another. Structuralism allows linguists to focus on the functional role of consonants in clusters, helping to identify whether these clusters are permissible or create phonotactic constraints in Tiv. It also allows linguists to look at phonological rules governing consonant combinations including whether specific clusters follow predictable patterns within the Tiv language sound system.

Analysis and Discussion

Tiv Consonant Clusters

The Tiv language allows the presence of different kinds of consonant clusters. There are clusters of two, three, four and even more. But for the sake of this study only the clusters of two, three and four are presented in the following tables for sample and analysis.

Table 1: Showing Consonant Cluster of two Consonant Sounds

Cluster	Words	Word Position	Meaning
/ŋg/	Ngun	Initial	This one
/by/	Abya	Midial	Small hoe
/mz/	Mzembe	initial	Pears
/ts/	Tsan	initial	Sharp

/ηd/	Ande	Midial	Tore
/ms/	Msambe	Initial	Scatter

The above table is a representation of consonant cluster of two combination distributed across the Tiv language in various words positions. It should however be understood that most of the above combination occur at the word medial position and most of them like: “ηg”, “ts”, “mz”, and “by” cannot be allowed to function at the word final position. The phonotactic constraint of the Tiv language allows them and many others a limited distribution across word positions (Ledefoged and Johnson (2014)). Understanding this clusters and their placement across words in the Tiv language has a long way to contribute to the entire Tiv phonology just as the theory of structural linguistics emphasised.

Table 2: Showing Consonant Cluster of three Combination

Consonant Cluster	Words	Position	Meaning
/mηg/	Mngu	Initial	I am
/mts/	Mtsem	Initial	Potash
/ηgw/	Ungwa	Midial	Hear
/tsw/	Tswer	Initial	Forbidden
/gby/	Igbyan	Midial	Kinsman
/mbw/	Mbwalaa	Initial	So small
/ηgy/	Ingyôr	Initial	Approaching
/dzw/	Dzwungwe	Initial	Mourn

Table 2 also contains various sounds as consonant combination as distributed in the sampled Tiv words that constitute their distribution and meanings. The peculiarity of Tiv language reveals that the sound representations in most cases do not differ from the orthographic representation which is done using the letters. Letters conveniently serve as sound in most cases. This explains why the Tiv phonological system has to be studied even by native speakers to understand its functionality.

Table 3: Showing Consonant Clusters of Four

Sounds	Words	Position	Meaning
/mηgb/	Mngbagh	Initial	To roast
/mtsw/	Mtswen	Initial	Alone
/mηgb/	Mngbough	Initial	Abundance
/rtsw/	Iortswam	Midial	People hate
/ghgb/	Mzoughgba	Midial	Gathering

As earlier stated, the Tiv language has proven from table three consonant combination of four sequence have found distributed in the sound system of Tiv language. While in comparison with other languages it may be very strange to see sounds like; /ghyb/, /rtsw/, /mtsw/ among other forming sounds combinations, in Tiv language they function as conventions and are not strange. Whereas in English language and other African languages this may not allow to function. This is because in most cases there are sounds that clearly represent the letters that constitute their written form. These clusters differ in various ways from one language to another. But understanding how, what they are, and how they operate in any language is a great advantage in understanding the whole phonological structure according to Structural Theory.

Contribution of Consonant Clusters to Tiv Phonology

From the structural perspective, the various aspects of Tiv language and the consonant clusters have contributed in giving Tiv phonology a unique structure which is not common with other languages. The

Tiv sound patterning system is not the same with that of English, Hausa, Igbo, Idoma and Igede respectively. The Tiv phonological system allows sounds combinations that are complex forming consonant clusters as a feature that is so distinct among other African languages. In a study, Arnott (1970) noted that Tiv allows consonants clusters that can be intricate, including sequences up to four consonants which is different with the phonotactic constraints seen in many languages in the region (Arnott, 1970). Similarly, the Tiv morphology contributes to the peculiar phonological arrangement or conventions as described by Orjime (1983), the combination of morphemes in Tiv often permits the formation of consonant clusters. Affixes and compound words bring many consonants together giving a distinctive feature of the Tiv language. Empirical research by linguists such as Pulleyblank (1988), also established the phonological rules governing consonant clusters in Tiv. This research accounts for how Tiv speakers manage and produce the clusters fluently, a characteristic that is not common and notable in the study of African language. Further, a comparative study with other languages shows the uniqueness of Tiv language to the phonetic structures of other various African languages and reveals that while many Batu languages prefer CV syllable structures, Tiv language allowance of complex cluster sets it apart. This comparison underscores the phonological distinctiveness of Tiv (Ladforger, 1968). In summary, the consonant clusters in Tiv language have contributed in various ways to the phonological structure of Tiv. It has not only made it unique but also reveal the rich pattern of consonant combination that are relevant in morphological development in Tiv.

Influence of Consonant Clusters on Tiv Syllables

The presence of consonant clusters in Tiv has brought phonological complexity in Tiv syllable structure. The Tiv syllables unlike other African languages accommodate consonant clusters of up to four consonant clusters. This complexity is evident in words where many shades of consonants appear consecutively within syllable impacting the syllabic patterns and phonotactics of the language (Orjime, 1983). For example; “Mzoughtar” meaning a boundary between countries, “torkpe”- the king is dead among others. The consonant clusters in these words are complex because a single cluster belongs to two different syllables. The /r/ and /t/ which forms a cluster in the first word belongs to two different syllables and /r/ and /kp/ can be separated to share as units in the first syllable and second syllable of the second word. This type of consonant cluster operating at the bounding of two syllables is called ambisyllabic consonant cluster or syllable-speaking consonant cluster.

Consonant clusters in Tiv syllables contribute to distinct phonological patterns. In Tiv language, the clusters are integrated into the Tiv phonological system, influencing rules of syllable structure and phonetic realization across different lexical items. Consonant clusters in Tiv have affected syllable structure by allowing complex sequences of consonants within syllables. For example, the word “tsen” (to dry) exemplifies a syllable with a complex onset cluster /ts/, which is permissible in Tiv phonology (Orjime, 1983).

Consonant clusters have really exact influence on the syllable of Tiv language produced in different results as seen in the practical and daily use of the language. In all the result of this influence has created complex onset syllable structure, complex coda syllables and ambisyllabic consonant clusters.

Conclusion

This research endeavour establishes that the Tiv language allows the existence of various consonant clusters ranging from two – four. However, the distribution of these consonant clusters is gradient in nature, meaning its distributional pattern is limited to specific areas across Tiv words. Additionally, these clusters have contributed to the entire phonological structure of the Tiv language making it complex and unique in comparison to other African languages. Finally, this phonological structure has great influence on Tiv syllable creating complex onset syllables, complex coda syllables and ambisyllabic syllables.

References

- Aboh, E.O. (2004). *The morphosyntax of complement* – Head sequences, Oxford Press.
Blench, R. (2019). *An atlas of Nigerian Languages*, Kay Williamsom Educational Foundation.

- Bohannan, P. (1953). *The Tiv of Central Nigeria* International African Institute.
- Bohannan, P. & Bohannan, L. (1969). *Tiv Economy*. Northwestern University Press.
- Crystal, D. (2011). *A dictionary of linguistics and phonetics*: Six Edition. Blackwell Publishing.
- Denham, K. & Lobeck, A. (2013). *Linguistics for everyone: An introduction*, 2nd Edition WADSWORTH CENGAGE Learning.
- Fromkim, V., Rodman, R. & Hyams, N. (2013). *An introduction in language*, Cengage Learning.
- Gerhardt, L. (1983). "Lexical and grammatical Notes on the Tiv Language" *Notes on Tiv language*. African Marburgensia.
- Hamann, C. & Sehmitz, Carmen (2005). *Phonetic and phonology: Reader for first year English linguistics*. University of Oldenburg.
- Ikoru, S.M. (1996). *The Kana Language*, CNWS Publications.
- Jones, E. (2019). *Shadows of the wind*, Edition House.
- Ladefoged, P. (1968). *A phonetic study of West African languages: An auditory-instrumental survey*, Cambridge University Press.
- Ladefoged, P. & Johnson, K. (2014). *A course in phonetics*. Cengage Learning.
- O'Grady, W. Archibald, J., Aronoff, M. and Reesmiller, J. (2010). *Contemporary Linguistic: An Introduction*. Bedford 1st. Martin's.
- Orjime, M.A. (1983). *Tiv Phonology and Morphology*. Ahmadu Bello University Press.
- Pulleblank, D. (1988). *Tiv Phonology Linguistic Inquiry*, Vol. 19, No.2, Pp. 233-257.
- Roach, P. (2010). *English Phonetics and Phonology: A practical Course* Fourth Edition Cambridge University Press.
- Sanssure, F. de. (1916). *Course in General Linguistic* (C. Bady & A. Sechehaye, Eds) (W. Baskin Trans) McGraw-Hill.
- Smith, J. (2022). *Mathematics for Every*. New York American Press.
- McWhorter, J.H. (2008) *Language Interrupted: Signs of Non-Native Acquisition in Standard Langue Grammars*. Oxford University Press.